

THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH IN THE BEVERAGE PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7677358>

Abstract. *In this article, it is considered to clarify the nature of marketing research and show its place in the modern market, analyze its forms, reveal its characteristics and study.*

Keywords: *enterprise, research, market, analysis, consumption, competition.*

Introduction. The President and the Government of our country are always paying attention to ensuring food safety and developing the food industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As stated in the address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, "In general, our people should be calm: the production of quality food products, the creation of a guaranteed reserve in this regard and their continuous delivery to the market, and ensuring price stability are given priority attention".

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results Improvement of the methodological basis of organizing marketing research in the market of thirst-quenching drinks, which is part of the consumer market. To achieve this goal, the following tasks are set in the dissertation:

- Explain the nature of marketing research and show its place in the modern market;
- Analysis of methods and forms of marketing research;
- Reveal the characteristics of marketing research in the consumer market;
- Study of marketing research conducted by the enterprise in the beverage market;

Marketing research involves organizing, collecting, processing and analyzing information. Such organization helps enterprises and firms to make marketing decisions in their activities and to reduce uncertainty as much as possible. Marketing is the object of research and serves the market, goods, trade (commerce), competitors, customers, pricing, advertising, opportunities for enterprises or firms. The unique qualities of conducting marketing research are that it helps to select the strategy and tactics of the enterprise and marketing activities and implement it on the basis of the conducted specific research. The content of marketing research is determined by its goals and objectives and requires two interrelated aspects: researching a specific market and researching the possibilities of enterprises or firms to enter the market and take a strong position there. Market research is the most common field of marketing research. It is conducted to collect information about the market in order to determine the activity of the enterprise.

Content of market research:

- determining the size of the market, analyzing its development trends and seasonal factors; market classification;
- study of market subjects, form and methods of trading in the market;

- determination of the current or expected shifts in the market structure in terms of age, regional location, social status, gender, family structure, purchasing behavior and other important criteria of the consumer structure, with increased attention to the issue;
- analysis of macroeconomic and other external factors affecting the market structure;
- analysis of product sales and its comparative contribution to the total sales amount in the market in terms of geographic and demographic segments, types of distribution channels, affiliation of consumer enterprises to the network, volume of goods turnover and price structure; this will determine the firm's market position, strengths and weaknesses.

A product marketing manager can quickly respond to market problems by managing the scope of all research related to that product. The following are part of the function of the marketing manager for a certain product: creating a marketing plan and budget for his product; to anticipate changes that may take place in the market in which this product is released; studying the activities of competitors and gathering information about them; coordinate their activities with the departments of the enterprise that affect the marketing of this product; budget compliance and price ratio control; from production to production of old goods and new goods.

Marketing research in the field of product research includes:

- analysis of intended new goods, selection for testing, checking whether they are suitable for consumers, physical characteristics and details specific to goods during consumption, packaging properties;
- to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of competing goods, that is, not only the goods of one's own company, but also the goods of competitors;
- study the possibilities of simplifying the assortment structure;
- the completeness of the range of products (products) in relation to competing products in the total market of the main goods or consumer sectors point-wise analysis;
- search for new ways of using manufactured products;
- studied the issues of technical equipment, after-sales service, additional service

There are different consumer segments in the market for low-alcohol and non-alcohol beverages, but some of them can be combined into a single targeted marketing effort;

Consumers can be divided according to the benefits (functions) that are the main for them when using soft and non-alcoholic drinks. Three main functions are highlighted:

refreshing,
reduce fatigue
improved mood.

Consider consumer groups for each function.

Refreshing. The majority of men and women who are students prefer to use energy drinks for strengthening (5% and 4% of respondents, respectively). Also, a large number of female students consume juice to satisfy the same need (4% of respondents). This trend is not surprising given the number of toning and energizing juices on the market today.

Reducing the feeling of fatigue. The most important segment for this function is student coffee drinkers. The share of women in this segment is 4%. Also, most of the female students consume energy drinks to reduce the feeling of fatigue (4% of respondents). With this function, one more segment can be distinguished - men who are enterprise workers who prefer to consume energy drinks and coffee to reduce the feeling of fatigue (respectively 4% of respondents).

Improved mood. The majority of business men prefer to consume energy drinks and beer to improve their mood (3% of each respondent). This segment is the most important for this segment.

For enterprises that sell their products in various markets, it is desirable that the organizational structure of the marketing service be focused on markets and consumers. Here, as a market, there can be a segment or an industry network that constitutes the same buyer. The reason for the introduction of the market manager is the need of the customers. The main markets are assigned to the market manager, who cooperates with the specialists of the software development department in various areas of the enterprise. A marketing strategy should be developed for each market.

The most common studies are market capacity determination, firm's share of market sales, market classification, sales analysis, competitor product research, and price research. It should be noted that companies in most cases turn to the services of special firms in advertising research and customer opinion research. In the remaining cases, firms rely on their own forces. At the same time, the head of marketing research should have a very good and comprehensive knowledge of information. Otherwise, the information may be incorrect, processed or out of date.

Determining the structure of marketing management means defining individual elements in the subject of marketing management, their subordination to each other, and determining their interrelationships in management decision-making and implementation. Such subordination and interaction can be different. This justifies the diversity of management structures. The following are most commonly considered:

- functional structure of management;
- management structure based on the commodity principle (commodity structure of management);
- management structure based on the regional principle (regional management structure);
- matrix management structure.

Concepts of management functions using the marketing concept. In order to choose a marketing activity, first of all, a marketing analysis is conducted. To the understanding of "Marketing analysis": marketing research, the concept of market segmentation, the selection of the target market and the characteristics of product positioning.

The functional structure of management is the most common structure in the activity of companies. In such a structure, the following departments report directly to the vice president or marketing director: service, sales, new goods, marketing research, communications, marketing management departments. The marketing management department coordinates the activities of other departments. For example, a pricing department can be established, and some of the above departments can be combined.

The functional structure of management is the simplest structure. However, with the growth of the product nomenclature and the expansion of the sales market, the effectiveness of such a management structure decreases.

1- picture Organizational structure of marketing service in large firms.

The most important stage in the process of conducting marketing research is their precise organization. The forms of organization of marketing research can be different: it uses its own research, involving foreign companies or in a mixed way.

Only large firms with a dedicated department can do marketing research on their own. Small firms can apply to a special organization or merge with other enterprises to transfer them. The majority of foreign firms prefer to use a mixed form in the organization of marketing research. Generally, outside organizations are tasked with conducting mass consumer surveys. In practice, all reputable foreign firms cooperate with market research institutes and (or) consulting organizations.

The main advantages and disadvantages of applying to foreign organizations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Advantages and disadvantages of outsourcing marketing research.

Advantages	Disadvantages
Professional skills of specialists; professional skills; research experience; in relation to consumers neutrality;	high cost of specialist services preservation of commercial secrets not guaranteed

The choice of the form of organization of marketing research is based on the following factors:

- the firm's market experience;
- availability of research staff;
- professional potential of employees;
- the position of the firm in the market and its goals;
- to the strategy and tactics of the firm's market activity.

Importance of decision making in marketing. First of all, let's look at the directions of marketing research before making a decision. And they are usually carried out in 5 major directions.

1. Advertising organization studies (buyer inspiration, advertising tests, types of advertising and their comparative effectiveness, etc.).

2. Strategic planning and organizational policy (short- and long-term forecasting and enterprise results, analysis of market locations, opportunities for new diversification development, operational gross analysis, analysis of the internal environment of the organization, export market observations, etc.).
3. Research on organizational responsibility (social responsibility of the organization on customer formation, environmental protection, etc.).
4. Market analysis (customer attitude to new goods, potential and opportunities of new goods, testing of new goods, problems of product coding and its verification, etc.).
5. Sales opportunities and marketing research (identification of competent or potential markets, analysis of market composition, analysis of changes in sales volume, conducting test marketing, studying sales promotion methods, etc.).

We will consider marketing research as a whole process and the tasks it should solve in detail in the following parts.

All the information collected in the marketing field is composed of analytical methods, developments, decision-making models, and computer programs as a decision-making subsystem in message management. It is natural that decisions made within the framework of management are based on certain sources and analytical results.

Research methods in marketing are justified by the necessity and obligation of comprehensive and systematic analysis of any market situation, its components related to various factors.

The principles of systematicity and complexity shown in conducting marketing research are based on the fact that when studying the external environment, primarily the market and its indicators, not only information about the state of the external environment of the enterprise, but also the company's strategic marketing goals and plans are taken into account - only then will the conducted research have a marketing character, etc. otherwise it will only be a study of the market, competitors, innovation factors, etc.

Marketing goals and objectives are defined in the section of the plan. A marketing objective is a final result that is intended to be achieved through marketing. Such final results are determined in relation to goods, consumers and markets. At the same time, the solution of the tasks expressed should ensure the achievement of the set goals. These objectives are required to:

- quantitatively based;
- ranked in order of importance;
- achieved in a certain period of time;
- real, i.e. it can be done in reality.

The fifth section of the plan deals with marketing strategies. Each such strategy envisages the implementation of a set of compatible measures that ensure the achievement of a specific goal. Such measures mean the following:

- market segmentation;
- identifying the target market;
- placement of goods and services in target segments;
- determining methods of entering the target market;
- development of marketing mix;
- time to market.

After the marketing strategies are determined, the sixth section of the plan develops an action program that specifies:

- what is done;
- when will it be done;
- who does;
- what resources are needed.

The seventh section of the plan shows the general estimate of marketing expenses. The costs of certain elements of the product movement policy, such as advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, and public relations, are also presented here.

The last section of the marketing plan describes the procedure of control over the implementation of the specified measures. Such control allows to evaluate the results of the company's activities and to take necessary measures to eliminate the identified deficiencies. Special attention is paid to the analysis of the achieved sales volume and the amount of profit obtained from it.

In order to ensure their viability in the conditions of a changing market economy, enterprises in operation will have to comprehensively analyze their strengths and weaknesses. The SWOT-analysis method is used to carry out this analysis. Based on this method, the company's strengths (S) and weaknesses (W), opportunities (O) and risks (T) are determined.

In recent years, as a result of the strengthening of the following three trends, it has been possible to collect marketing information in a better quality and on a wider scale.

1. Moving from local level marketing to general marketing scale. As firms and businesses are constantly expanding their market territory, it becomes increasingly difficult for their managers to get to know all of their customers personally. Therefore, it is necessary to find new ways to collect marketing information, to organize it, to determine the scope of information necessary for further marketing research.

2. Transition from consumer need to consumer demand. As consumers' incomes increase, they become more discerning in their choice of goods and services, so it is necessary to find criteria that can easily explain consumer behavior. Studying the causes of consumer demand, identifying unsatisfied needs and requirements, dividing consumers into groups (segments) that demand different goods and services according to the type, quality, and quantity, and trying to find a separate, unique demand within each segment through marketing research.

3. Shifting to non-price competition instead of price competition. Thanks to scientific and technical advances, favorable conditions are created for the use of methods of competition that are not related to price. becomes the main factor of competition. At such times, information on "how the market is affected by the methods used" becomes important. In such conditions, enterprises and firms start placing orders for conducting marketing research. In the conditions of the market economy, enterprises and firms will not be able to control the market unless the goods and services are coordinated according to the actual needs and requirements of the consumers.

Marketing research involves organizing, collecting, processing and analyzing information. Such organization helps enterprises and firms to make marketing decisions in their activities and to reduce uncertainty as much as possible. Marketing is the object of research and serves the market, goods, trade (commerce), competitors, customers, pricing, advertising, opportunities for enterprises or firms. The unique qualities of conducting marketing research are that it helps to select the strategy and tactics of the enterprise and marketing activities and implement it on the

basis of the conducted specific research. The content of marketing research is determined by its goals and objectives and requires two interrelated aspects: researching a specific market and researching the possibilities of enterprises or firms to enter the market and take a strong position there. Market research is the most common field of marketing research. It is conducted to collect information about the market in order to determine the activity of the enterprise.

REFERENCES

1. Basovsky LE Marketing: Course lecture. - M.: INFRA-M, 2010. - 219 p.
2. Bronnikova TS Marketing: theory, practice: uchebnoe posobie / TS Bronnikova – 2nd ed., pererab. i dop. - M.: KNORUS, 2010. - 208 p.
3. Gerasimov BI, Mozgov NN Marketingovyie issledovaniya rynka: uchebnoe posobie / BI Gerasimov, NN Mozgov. - M.: FORUM, 2009. - 336 p.: il.
4. Paramonova TN Marketing: uchebnoe posobie / TN Paramonova, IN
5. Ibragimov RG Marketing. Darslik, T.: "East", 2002
6. Krasnyuk; pod ed. TN Paramonovoy. - M.: KNORUS, 2010. - 190 p.
7. Rozova NK Marketing. - SPb.: Peter, 2008. -176 p.
8. Fattokhov AA, RNKarimova distributor activities in the market. Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2009.-227b.
9. Yusupov MA, Abdurakhmonova N. Marketing. - T.: Economy, 2007.
10. Kasimova MS, Abduhalilova LT Marketing studies. - T.: TDIU, 2010.-157 p.
11. Kasimova MS, Samadov AN, Ergashkhodzhaeva Sh.J. Economics of commercial enterprises. - T.: TDIU, 2010.163 p.
12. Kalka Regine. Marketing / Regine Kalka, Andrea Messen; (per. s German. MV Lapshinova). – 3rd ed., ster. - M.: SmartBuk, 2010. - 126 p.: il.
13. Karpova SV International marketing for students of the university / SV Karpova. - Rostov n/d: Phoenix, 2010. - 184 p.
14. Karpova SV Praktikum po mejdunarodnomu marketing: uchebnoe posobie / SV Karpova. - M.: KNORUS, 2010. - 200 p.
15. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
16. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
17. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //Central Asian Journal Of Innovations On Tourism Management And Finance. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5.
18. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Innovative Strategies Of Tourism Development In Uzbekistan //European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
19. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
20. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact

- Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.
21. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
 22. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozиковich M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
 23. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
 24. Azimovna M. S., Shohruxhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //Barqarorlik Va Yetakchi Tadqiqotlar Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnal. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
 25. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
 26. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhruxhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-12.